

Scientific article

Tuning of a holistic synchronous multi-objective framework for wind farm flow control

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Abstract: *Wind farm flow control has traditionally focused on maximizing energy yield, often treating structural load mitigation as a constraint rather than an objective in its own right. Developing a multi-objective framework is not trivial and becomes increasingly complex with a growing number of objective functions. Desirability functions provide an analytical formulation that enables the operator to intuitively translate these objectives into an effective reference frame. This work introduces a holistic, synchronous multi-objective framework for wind farm flow control that integrates operator-defined desirability functions to jointly optimize for energy yield and structural loading. By employing tailored one-sided desirability functions for yield and damage equivalent loads (DELs), the framework enables the prioritization of objectives through distinct control strategies that shift between wind-farm-level (WFL) and wind-turbine-level (WTL). The methodology is demonstrated on a three-turbine IEA 37 test case using surrogate load and wake models within the PyWake environment. Maps of the desirability tuning space reveal how operator preferences influence the resulting control strategies and identify optimal operating regions that balance performance and structural integrity. The results demonstrate the potential of desirability-based control formulations to open wind farm operation from purely economic optimization toward holistic decision-making.*

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